

Vol:1, Issue: 3 pp: 237-246

JEL Codes: I00,M1,J00

RAFAEL L.O. (2020). "Recipients' Perception on the Social Services Programs of Rtnmc and Cbnc at Rio Tuba, Bataraza, Palawan"

Vol: 1 Issue: 3 pp: 237-246

Keywords: *perception, recipients, social services, satisfaction, management*

Article Type Research Article

Recipients' Perception on the Social Services Programs of Rtnmc and Cbnc at Rio Tuba, Bataraza, Palawan

Arrived Date
16.07.2020

Accepted Date
19.07.2020

Published Date
31.07.2020

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the perceptions of the recipients towards the social services provided by the RTNMC and CBNC among the target barangays beneficiaries and was conducted in eleven (11) partner barangays which includes Culandanum, Igang-Igang, Iwahig, Ocayan, Rio Tuba, Sandoval, Sapa, Sarong, Sumbiling, Taratak, and Tarusan with 88 LGU Officials and 252 direct recipients using questionnaire as an interview guide. Results reveals that LGU Officials and direct recipients were Moderately Satisfied in health services, human resources, infrastructure and development programs and governance and management including the mode of implementation of such services. Thus, it was recommended that companies should develop management strategies that will improve the delivery social services, Likewise, the LGU Officials should perform community consultation regarding the priority needs of the people and maintain collaborative efforts with the constituents for successful implementation of the project. Finally, direct recipients should cooperate with the LGU officials and company personnels for the success of implementation of programs and projects.

INTRODUCTION

Ethics are code of values and principles that govern the action of a person or group of people regarding what is right or wrong. Therefore, ethics set standards to what is good or bad in organizational conduct and decision making. In the business setting, being ethical means applying principles of honesty and fairness to relationships with coworkers and customers. They further stressed that the concepts of business ethics is defined as the rules, standards, codes or principles that provides guidance for appropriate behavior in managerial decisions relating to the operations of the corporations and business relationship with the society. It applies to all aspects of business conduct and is relevant to the conduct of individuals and entire organizations (Adda et.al, 2016).

Sroka and Szántó (2018) cited that business ethics also known as corporate social ethics or a form of applied ethics that examines the principles and moral or ethical problems which arise in in a business environment and it applies to all aspects of business conduct and is relevant to the conduct of individuals and entire organizations. This information somewhat agrees Gheraia et.al (2019) that Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept whereby companies decide voluntarily to contribute to a better society and a cleaner environment. In this way, CSR is about companies manage the business processes to produce an overall positive impact on society. They further stated that according to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development in its publication "Corporate Social Responsibility is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well

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as the local communities and society at large. Thus, social service as an activity designed to promote social well-being; specifically, an organized philanthropic assistance (<http://www.merriam-webster.com>). The statement was clearly elaborated in the Chapter 10 of Republic Act No. 7942 (Philippine Mining Act of 1995) provides that “the contractor shall assist in the development of its mining community, the promotion of the general welfare of its inhabitants and the development of science and mining technology”. Created activities under the Social Development and Management Programs were establishment and construction, development and maintenance of infrastructure such as community schools, hospital, churches, roads, bridges etc. Establishment of livelihood industries including reforestation through agreement contracts to be issued by the DENR utilizing fruits trees; and using facilities within the mine camp, such as hospitals and schools by members of host and neighboring communities. All activities will be handled and managed by a Community Relation Officer (CRO) as a company official who will serve as a link between the company and the host and neighboring communities in the implementation of the SDMP. Yet, peoples’ perception may affect one programs on the manner of its planning, implementation and managing.

Statement of the Problem

Given the fact that social services are one of the role of any established organizations, the mining companies such as Rio Tuba Nickel Mining Corporation (RTNMC) and Coral Bay Nickel Corporation (CBNC) employed the same to help people in the community, thus the study aims to answer the following questions: (1) what is the recipients’ perception on the impact of social services programs of RTNMC and CBNC in terms of: a. health services; b. human resources, infrastructure and development programs; and c. governance and management; what is the mode of implementation of the social services of RTNMC and CBNC;

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to determine the perceptions of the recipients towards the social services provided by the RTNMC and CBNC among the recipients. Specifically, it aims to: (1) Determine the recipients’ perception on social services programs of RTNMC and CBNC in terms of; a. health services; b. human resources, infrastructure and development programs; and c. governance and management; (2) to find out the mode of implementation of the social services of RTNMC and CBN

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the study

This study was conducted in the selected barangays of Bataraza, Palawan specifically the barangays of Culandanum, Igang-Igang, Iwahig, Ocayan, Rio Tuba, Sandoval, Sapa, Sarong, Sumbiling, Taratak, and Tarusan,

Research Design

Descriptive research using survey method was employed in this study as to recipients’ perception towards the social services programs of RTNMC and CBNC particularly on the aspects of health services, human resources, infrastructures and development programs and governance and management and process of implementation.

Respondents of the Study

All barangay officials and 252 direct recipients of the programs of the target beneficiary barangays served as the respondents of this study.

Sampling Procedure

All barangay officials of the respective target beneficiary barangays were included in the study. On the other hand, the research also used purposive sampling in the selection of the direct recipients of the program in convenient sampling using the Slovin’s Formula 5% margin of error.

The formula is given as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

- N = sampling size
 N = population size
 E = desired margin of error

The purposive sampling was used to determine the samples of respondents that represent the total population of the direct recipients.

Instrumentation

A set of questionnaire was prepared and used in this study that based on the social services extended by the companies to the target barangay beneficiaries. The interview schedule is composed of two (2) parts. The part I focus on the agreed perceptions of the respondents on the impact of the projects and programs extended to them and Part II pertains to the mode of implementation of social services of RTNMC and CBNC towards the partner barangays.

Data Collection Procedure

Written consent from the barangay officials, RTNMC, CBNC was requested prior to data collection. After the request has been approved, the prepared questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Respondents were visited and interviewed in their barangays, in their homes while they are doing their chores.

Treatment of Data

Different statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the data in which the most were analyzed in a descriptive measure using frequency counts, percentages and means. Moreover, to interpret the respondents' perception on social services extended by the RTNMC and CBNC towards their respective barangay, a Likert's five (5) point rating scale was used in the data analysis in describing the respondents satisfaction and perception level towards the social services provided by the companies as criterion variables for its statistical validity and assessment.

Numerical Weight	Interval Estimate	Description
5	4.50 – 5.00	Extremely Satisfied
4	3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfied
3	2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Satisfied
2	1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Satisfied
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not at all Satisfied

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recipients' Perception on the Impact of Health Services

Table 1a presents the respondents perceptions towards the health services provided by the Rio Tuba Nickel Mining Corporation (RTNMC) and Coral Bay Nickel Corporation (CBNC).

The data shows that LGU Officials gave an over-all mean rating of (3.06) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* in the provision of health services provided by the company which could be described as follows; medical assistance to patients attended at RTNFI Hospital and budgetary allocation for patients attended at RTNFI Hospital (3.31); the distribution of health workers tools and equipment had a mean rating of (3.27). A (3.25) mean rating was given to budgetary assistance for the continuous education of health laborers followed by the budgetary assistance for the improvements of health center facility (3.24); budgetary assistance for health workers (3.23); budgetary assistance for the renovation of health center (3.19); provision of BHW training (2.97); budgetary assistance for dengue and malaria prevention program (2.84); medical mission in the barangay (2.80); existence of malaria and dengue prevention program (2.65); production of IEC health materials (2.63); the distribution of water treatment facility got the least mean rating of (2.58); while provision of over the counter medicines got the highest mean of (3.55) which could be describe as *Very Satisfied*.

Meanwhile, the direct recipients obtains an over-all mean of (3.05) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* as also shown in the provision of over the counter medicine (3.43) followed by distribution of health workers tools and equipment (3.40); budget salary assistance for health workers (3.38); assistance for improvements of health center facility (3.35); budgetary assistance for dengue and malaria prevention program (3.15); provision of BHW training (3.12); existence of malaria and dengue prevention program (3.0); budgetary assistance for the continuous education of health laborers (2.88); and the medical mission in the barangay (2.53); while budget assistance for the renovation of health center got a mean rating of (2.0) with a descriptive rating of *Slightly Satisfied*. On the contrary, the budgetary assistance for patients attended at RTNFI Hospital obtained a mean rating of (3.78) with a descriptive rating of *Very Satisfied* followed by budgetary allocation for patients attended at RTNFI Hospital (3.67); and distribution of water treatment facility (3.51). Of all the health services provided by RTNMC and CBNC among the direct recipients, it was the budgetary assistance for patients attended at RTNFI Hospital obtained the highest rating (3.78) with a descriptive rating of *Very Satisfied*; while budget assistance for the renovation of health center got a mean rating of (2.0) with a descriptive rating of *Slightly Satisfied*. The result implied that, all respondents were aspiring for an effective and efficient delivery of the health services programs of the companies.

Table 1a. Recipients' perception towards the health services.

Aspects	LGU Officials f(n=88)		Direct Recipients f(n=252)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR
Health Services				
Provision of BHW Training	2.97	MS	3.12	MS
Budgetary assistance for continuous education of Health Laborers	3.25	MS	2.88	MS
Distribution of Health Workers tools and equipment	3.27	MS	3.40	MS
Existence of Malaria and Dengue prevention program	2.65	MS	3.00	MS
Budgetary assistance for Dengue and Malaria prevention program	2.84	MS	3.15	MS

Medical assistance to patients attended at RTNFI Hospital	3.31	MS	3.78	VS
Budgetary allocation for patients attended at RTNFI Hospital	3.31	MS	3.67	VS
Medical mission in the barangay	2.80	MS	2.53	MS
Budget salary assistance for the renovation of health center	3.19	MS	2.00	MS
Budget salary assistance for Health Workers	3.23	MS	3.38	MS
Distribution of water treatment facility	2.58	MS	3.51	MS
Distribution of IEC materials	2.63	MS	1.49	NS
Provision of over the counter medicines	3.55	VS	3.43	MS
Assistance for the improvement of Health Center facility.	3.24	MS	3.35	MS
Grand Mean:	3.06	MS	3.05	MS

Legend:

- 4.50 - 5.00 - Extremely Satisfied
- 3.50 - 4.49 - Very Satisfied
- 2.50 - 3.49 - Moderately Satisfied
- 1.50 - 2.49 - Slightly Satisfied
- 1.00 - 1.49 - Not at all Satisfied

Recipients' Perception on Human Resources, Infrastructure and Development Programs

The results of the study reveal the perception of the LGU Officials towards the human resources and development programs provided by the companies was (2.86) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied*. Study further shows that provision for the improvement of barangay facilities was given a rating of (3.33) and this was followed by provision of employment (2.99); establishment of multi-purpose hall (2.98); budgetary assistance for covered gymnasium (2.97); and budgetary assistance for tribal festival (2.94).

Further, the provision of gadgets to barangay organization was given a rating of (2.86) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* followed by distribution of water pumps (2.85); construction of tribal houses (2.82); distribution of utility vehicles (2.81); provision of budget for barangay road repair as assisted by LGU and provincial Government Unit (2.80); establishment of pavements in the barangay (2.78); while provision of livelihood trainings and seminars and construction of GK village obtain the same rating (2.77); provision of lighting facility on different churches (2.74); and provision of generator set among barangays (2.55). It has been noted that, the provision for the improvement of barangay facilities (3.33) was given the highest rating in all projects while provision of generator set among barangays (2.55) was the least perceived by the LGU Officials.

The over-all rating given by the direct recipients on human resources and development programs was (2.90) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* however only one program, construction of GK village was given a mean rating of (3.52) which describe as *Very Satisfied*. The data further shows distribution of water pumps was given a mean rating of (3.43) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately*

Satisfied followed by improvement of barangay facility (3.37); establishment of multi-purpose hall (3.40); provision of employment (3.31); provision of budget for barangay road repair as assisted by LGU and Provincial Government Unit (3.19); budgetary assistance for tribal festival (3.18); establishment of pavements in the barangay (3.08); distribution of water pumps (3.07); construction of tribal houses (3.0); provision of gadgets to barangay organization (2.92); distribution of utility vehicles (2.37). However, the provision of lighting facility on different churches was given a rating of (2.01) which was described as *Slightly Satisfied* followed by provision of livelihood trainings and seminars (1.67). It was been observed that direct recipients gave a highest rating of (3.52) in the construction of GK village which is described as *Very Satisfied* while provision of livelihood trainings and seminars got the least rating (1.67) with a descriptive rating of *Slightly Satisfied* (Table 1b).

Table 1b. Recipients' perception towards the human resources, infrastructure and development programs.

Aspects	LGU Officials f(n=88)		Direct Recipients f(n=252)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR
	Human Resources and Development			
Establishment of Multi- purpose hall	2.98	MS	3.40	MS
Improvement of barangay facilities	3.33	MS	3.37	MS
Provision of gadgets to barangay organization	2.86	MS	2.92	MS
Establishment of pavement in the barangay	2.78	MS	3.09	MS
Budgetary assistance for tribal festival	2.94	MS	3.18	MS
Budgetary assistance for covered gymnasium	2.97	MS	1.89	SS
Construction of Tribal Houses	2.82	MS	3.00	MS
Provision of lighting facility on different churches	2.74	MS	2.01	SS
Construction of GK Village	2.77	MS	3.52	VS
Provision of genset among barangays	2.55	MS	3.07	MS
Distribution of water pumps	2.85	MS	3.43	MS
Provision of employment	2.99	MS	3.31	MS
Provision on livelihood seminars and trainings	2.77	MS	1.67	SS
Provision of budget for barangay road repair as assisted by LGU and Provincial Government Unit	2.80	MS	3.19	MS
Distribution of utility vehicles	2.81	MS	2.37	SS
Grand Mean:	2.86	MS	2.90	MS

Legend:

- 4.50 - 5.00 - Extremely Satisfied
- 3.50 - 4.49 - Very Satisfied
- 2.50 - 3.49 - Moderately Satisfied

- 1.50 - 2.49 - Slightly Satisfied
 1.00 - 1.49 - Not at all Satisfied

Recipients' Perception towards Governance and Management of Programs and Project

Table 1c shows the governance and management as perceived by the respondents. It reveals that the LGU Officials and direct recipients gave an over-all rating of (2.93) and (3.03) with an adjectival rating of *Moderately Satisfied*. As to the measure on the resolution and conflict between LGU Officials and company personnel, the LGU Officials gave a highest mean rating of (3.18) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* followed by representation of LGU Officials and company personnel during SDMP planning (3.14); employment of project assessment whenever project is being done (3.02); and monitoring of the project on its on-going process; while the least mean rating (2.39) was given by the respondents on the aspect of giving of incentives to LGU hired laborer which is described as *Slightly Satisfied*.

On the contrary, the direct recipients perceived monitoring of the project on its on-going process was given a highest mean rating of (3.44) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* followed by employment of project assessment whenever project is being done (3.41); representation of LGU Officials and company personnel during SDMP planning (3.38); measures on resolution and conflict between LGU Officials and company personnel (2.52); while giving of incentives to LGU hired laborers got the least mean rating of (2.38) which describe as *Slightly Satisfied*.

Table 1c. Recipients' perception towards the governance and management of programs and projects.

Aspects	LGU Officials f(n=88)		Direct Recipients f(n=252)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR
	Governance and Management			
Measures on the resolution and conflict between LGU Officials and company personnel	3.18	MS	2.52	MS
Representation of LGU Officials and company personnel during SDMP planning	3.14	MS	3.38	MS
Monitoring of the Project on its on- going process	2.94	MS	3.44	MS
Employment of project assessment whenever project is being done	3.02	MS	3.41	MS
Giving of incentives to LGU hired laborers	2.39	SS	2.38	SS
Measures on the resolution and conflict between LGU Officials and company personnel	3.18	MS	2.52	MS
Representation of LGU Officials and company personnel during SDMP planning	3.14	MS	3.38	MS
Grand Mean:	2.93	MS	3.03	MS

Legend:

- 4.50 - 5.00 - Extremely Satisfied
 3.50 - 4.49 - Very Satisfied
 2.50 - 3.49 - Moderately Satisfied
 1.50 - 2.49 - Slightly Satisfied
 1.00 - 1.49 - Not at all Satisfied

Mode of Implementation of Social Services

As to mode of implementation, results reveal in Table 4 that LGU Officials are Moderately Satisfied in the process of implementation of the company's programs and projects whereas, it obtain an over-all mean rating of (2.77). It further shows that provision of resolution, project request prior to project implementation was given a mean rating of (3.14) with a descriptive rating of Moderately Satisfied followed by accepting LGU's decision in project re-alignment (3.07); and hiring of technical expert's advice before project implementation (2.53); and hiring of laborer or contract person to do the project (2.35). Further, direct recipients perception presents that the provision of resolution, project request prior to project implementation was given a highest mean rating (3.31) which describe as Moderately Satisfied followed by accepting LGU's decision in project re-alignment (3.10); hiring of technical expert's advice before project implementation (2.90) and the least mean rating (2.67) was given to the aspect of hiring of laborer or contract person to do the project (Table 2).

Table 2. Mode of implementation of the social services.

Aspects	LGU Officials		Direct Recipients	
	f(n=88)		f(n=252)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR
Mode of Implementation				
Provision of resolution, project request prior to project implementation	3.14	MS	3.31	MS
Accepting LGU's decision on project re- alignment	3.07	MS	3.10	MS
Hiring technical expert's advice before project implementation	2.53	MS	2.90	MS
Hiring of laborers / contract person to do the project	2.35	SS	2.67	MS
Grand Mean:	2.77	MS	3.03	MS

Legend:

- 4.50 - 5.00 - Extremely Satisfied
 3.50 - 4.49 - Very Satisfied
 2.50 - 3.49 - Moderately Satisfied
 1.50 - 2.49 - Slightly Satisfied
 1.00 - 1.49 - Not at all Satisfied

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study aimed to determine the perceptions of the recipients towards the social services provided by the RTNMC and CBNC among the target barangays beneficiaries and was conducted in eleven (11) partner barangays which includes Culandanum, Igang-Igang, Iwahig, Ocayan, Rio Tuba, Sandoval, Sapa, Sarong, Sumbiling, Taratak, and Tarusan with 88 LGU Officials and 252 direct recipients using questionnaire as an interview guide.

Results reveals that LGU Officials and direct recipients gave an over-all mean rating of (3.06) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* in the provision of health services provided by the company such as distribution of health workers tools and equipment, budgetary assistance for the continuous education of health laborers followed by the budgetary assistance for the improvements of health center facility budgetary assistance for health workers salary, budgetary assistance for the renovation of health center. Although there are some programs that are perceived as *Very Satisfied* (3.55) such as provisions of over the counter medicines as affirmed by the LGU Officials and Medical assistance to patients attended at RTNFI Hospital (3.78) and Budgetary allocation for patients attended at RTNFI Hospital (3.67) as attested by direct recipients.

Moreover, LGU Officials perception towards the human resources and development programs provided by the companies was (2.86) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* in the provision for the improvement of barangay facilities, followed by provision of employment (2.99); establishment of multi-purpose hall (2.98); budgetary assistance for covered gymnasium (2.97); and budgetary assistance for tribal festival (2.94) and other social services programs. Likewise the over-all rating given by the direct recipients in all human resources and development programs was (2.90) with a descriptive rating of *Moderately Satisfied* however only one program, construction of GK village was given a mean rating of (3.52) which describe as *Very Satisfied*.

It further reveals that both LGU Officials and direct recipients perceived the governance and management of social services programs as *Moderately Satisfied* in all its aspects and dealings.

Finally, both LGU Officials and direct recipients perceived that they were *Moderately Satisfied* on the mode of implementation of social services of the companies which gave an over- all rating of (2.77) and (3.03) respectively.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, the following conclusions were drawn;

1. Respondents were moderately satisfied on the social services provided by the RTNMC and CBNC towards the target barangays beneficiaries.
2. Respondents slightly agree that social services were implemented
3. Companies should improve their processes in the mode of implementing their programs and projects to ensure its success.

Recommendations

After a thorough examination of the findings, the researcher would like to recommend the following;

For the RTNMC and CBNC

1. Develop management strategies that will improve the delivery social services.
2. Maintain a collaborative effort with the target barangay beneficiaries for a strong relationship and successful program implementation.
3. Conduct an assessment studies to determine the priority needs of the community.
4. Continuously support the community needs through programs and projects of social services.

For the LGU Officials

1. Continuously assist the companies in the delivery of programs and projects.
2. Perform community consultation regarding the priority needs of the people.
3. Maintain collaborative efforts with the constituents for successful implementation of the project.
4. Established a strong linkage between the companies, community folks and local stake holders.

For the Direct Recipients

1. Cooperate with the LGU officials and company personnel for the success of implementation of programs and projects.
2. Giving of importance to the programs and projects being implemented by the concerned agencies.

For the Future Researchers

1. A parallel study should be conducted in the other areas of the country.

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